

most effective against stem borer and leaffolder. Treated plants yielded 4–5 t/ha compared with 1.9–2.5 t/ha for the untreated control. It was most effective in both seasons and at both dosages. Isofenphos (0.5 kg ai/ha) and thiocy-

clam hydrogen oxalate 90 SP successfully reduced yield losses to yellow stem borer and leaffolder (see table). Carbo-sulfan, an analogue of carbofuran, was effective against stem borer and leaf-folder. Fenvalerate, a synthetic pyre-

throid, was effective against leaffolder at reproductive phase of the crop under rainy season conditions. Bendiocarb and phosalone were least effective. ✎

Seasonal incidence of rice whorl maggot at Tirur, India

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In the Chingleput district of Tamil Nadu, rice is planted continuously, depending on availability of water from lift irrigation wells. Seasonal incidence of rice whorl maggot was studied in 36 planting dates 10 days apart at Tirur PES. The first planting was 10 May 1980, the last 30 April 1981. Six varieties were evaluated without chemical protection.

Seasonal incidence of rice whorl maggot at Tirur, India, 1980-81.

Planting date	Damage mean (%)
10-5-1980	8.7
20-5	6.5
30-5	7.8
10-6	6.8
20-6	5.0
30-6	4.4
10-7	16.7
20-7	18.4
30-7	13.2
10-8	10.1
20-8	12.9
30-8	10.9
10-9	13.6
20-9	10.1
30-9	15.4
10-10	20.6
20-10	26.3
30-10	20.6
10-11	14.0
20-11	14.5
30-11	13.6
10-12	15.8
20-12	26.9
30-12	33.3
10-1-1981	32.6
20-1	27.6
30-4	17.4
10-2	18.7
20-2	10.1
2-3	11.2
11-3	12.6
21-3	11.7
31-3	11.3
10-4	14.0
20-4	10.2
30-4	14.4

CD (4.99)

Whorl maggot damage to tillers was assessed 30 days after transplanting (DT).

Whorl maggot damage was less than 10% in May-June plantings, 10–20% in July, August, September, February, March, and April plantings, and above

20% in October, December, and January plantings (see table). Pest damage was significantly less on crops planted on 20 and 30 June, and significantly higher on crops planted 20 December to 20 January. The varieties were equally susceptible. ✎

A new scarabaeid beetle pest of dry-land rice in Bangladesh

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Since 1978 a scarabaeid beetle, *Heteronychus lioderes* Redtenbacher, has

caused severe damage to dryland rice in Noakhali, Chittagong, Comilla, and Mymensingh, and on the islands of Sandwip and Hatiya.

Farmers on Sandwip Island, where the beetle is called *talkora* reported a serious outbreak of the pest during April and May 1980 in aus rice (March-August). Aman (July-December) and boro (November-June) crops have also been attacked during dry periods.

Adult beetles are black and about 16 mm long (Fig. 1). They damage plants

1. Scarabaeid beetles, genus *Heteronychus*, that have damaged dryland rice in Bangladesh.

2. Adult scarabaeid beetles chew the base of rice stems just above the roots.

by chewing the base of the stem just above the roots (Fig. 2). Although the Indian beetle usually damages rice seedlings, the pest attacks dryland rice at all stages in Bangladesh. If plants are attacked after flowering, whitehead-like damage occurs. In early stages of an attack, rows of dead hills are observed near levees. Whole fields are later damaged. Beetles are found in sandy or sandy loam soils.

Although no control experiment has been conducted, aldrin, dieldrin, heptachlor, carbofuran, fenitrothion, and malathion have been tentatively recommended for control. If irrigation water is available, flooding the fields for a few days is also successful.

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Granular insecticides for control of major rice insects in Thailand

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Insecticide plays a major role in rice insect control in Thailand. Insecticide importation was 10,045 t in 1980 and has increased 2-3 times during the last 6 years. About 20% of the insecticide was used for rice. Monocrotophos has been

used for many years as a foliar spray but is now widely distributed in local markets in granular form. This study evaluated the effectiveness of monocrotophos and other granular insecticides for rice insect control.

In a greenhouse test monocrotophos effectively controlled brown planthopper (BPH) and gall midge (GM) as compared to carbofuran (see table). Diazinon also caused high BPH mortality and was moderately effective for GM. In a field experiment, contradictory results were found. Monocrotophos and dia-

zinon did not control GM but carbofuran, followed by chlorpyrifos and quinalphos, was effective. Although stem borer incidence was low, carbofuran-treated plants had fewest deadhearts. Diazinon-treated plants had more deadhearts than the untreated check at 60 days after transplanting. Carbofuran treatment produced the highest grain yield. Diazinon and monocrotophos treatments did not produce yields significantly different from the untreated check. Reasons for contradictory greenhouse and field results for monocroto-

Effect of granular insecticides on rice gall midge, brown planthopper (BPH), and stem borers in Thailand, 1981^a

Treatment	Greenhouse		Field				
	Silver shoots (%)	BPH mortality (%)	Silvershoots (%)		Deadhearts (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)
	20 DI	4 DAT	30 DT	60 DT	30 DT	60 DT	
Carbofuran	1 a	94 a	4 a	1 a	0.9 a	0.4 a	2.14 a
Chlorpyrifos	52 cd	—	6 ab	5 ab	2.6 a	5.1 ab	1.91 b
Quinalphos	26 bc	—	4 a	13 b	1.0 a	4.7 ab	1.87 b
Diazinon	20 b	100 a	15 bc	49 c	2.4 a	12.7 c	1.24 cd
Cartap	—	—	21 cd	63 d	0.6 a	5.4 ab	1.10 d
Monocrotophos	8 ab	98 a	26 d	50 c	1.0 a	7.6 bc	1.21 cd
Untreated control	65 d	14 b	22 d	41 c	1.9 a	6.1 ab	1.34 c

^aGreenhouse tests were conducted at the Rice Protection Research Center, Bangkok. The field trial was at Chumpae Rice Experiment Station, Khon-kaen. Insecticides (1 kg ai/ha) were applied to 20-day-old rice planted in clay pots for greenhouse trial, and 3 times at 15, 30, and 45 DT in the field trial. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$). DI = days after infestation. DAT = days after treatment. DT = days after transplanting.